

Study on the Competitiveness of Aggregate Transport Lines in Villahermosa, Tabasco

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Resumen

Este artículo presenta el proceso de selección metodológica para evaluar la competitividad de las líneas de transporte de agregados pétreos en Villahermosa, Tabasco, considerando las particularidades del entorno operativo local. A partir de la revisión de cinco modelos analíticos ampliamente reconocidos, Cinco Fuerzas de Porter, Diamante de Porter, Mapa de Competitividad del BID, Modelo DCO de Martín Álvarez y Método Delphi, se realizó una comparación técnica basada en criterios como adaptabilidad, participación de expertos, requerimientos de información y aplicabilidad para la mejora. Los resultados demostraron que el método Delphi es el más adecuado para contextos donde los datos son limitados, pero existe una amplia experiencia empírica. Su enfoque participativo, iterativo y estructurado permite identificar y jerarquizar los factores clave que afectan la competitividad, integrando el conocimiento de los propios actores del sector. La herramienta no solo cumple una función diagnóstica, sino que también habilita la construcción colectiva de soluciones estratégicas orientadas al fortalecimiento del sector transporte.

Abstract

This article presents the methodological selection process for evaluating the competitiveness of crushed stone transport lines in Villahermosa, Tabasco, considering the specific characteristics of the local operational environment. Based on a review of five widely recognized analytical models, Porter's Five Forces, Porter's Diamond, IDB Competitiveness Map, DCO Model by Martín Álvarez, and the Delphi Method, a technical comparison was carried out using criteria such as adaptability, expert participation, data requirements, and practical applicability. The results showed that the Delphi method is best suited for contexts where statistical data is limited but empirical knowledge is abundant. Its participatory, iterative, and structured approach allows for the identification and prioritization of key competitiveness factors, incorporating insights from the sector's own actors. Beyond diagnostics, the tool supports the collective construction of strategic solutions aimed at strengthening the transportation sector.

Palabras Clave: Competitividad, Transporte, Agregados, Metodología, Delphi

Keywords: Competitiveness, Transport, Aggregates, Methodology, Delphi

1. INTRODUCTION

Competitiveness in land transportation is a key factor for the economic and social development of regions, particularly in those where the distribution of construction materials, such as crushed stone aggregates, plays a fundamental role. In Villahermosa, Tabasco, the transport of these aggregates directly impacts the efficiency of the logistics chain and urban dynamism (González, 2016).

This industrial segment faces various challenges, such as high operating costs, deficiencies in road infrastructure, logistical inefficiencies, and limited technological adoption, which affect their competitiveness compared to more efficient markets, Gil (2017). Analyzing this environment requires an approach that combines critical operational, economic, and technological variables for the sector.

In order to identify improvement opportunities and design effective competitive strategies, this article proposes the selection of an analytical method that objectively measures the competitiveness of aggregate transport lines. This method will integrate both internal and external factors, adapting to the specific regional context.

The transport lines

A transport line is an operational or business unit dedicated to the systematic movement of goods, commodities, or materials between points of origin and destination, generally within a structured logistics framework (González, 2016). In the case of aggregate transport, these lines operate heavy-duty vehicles (such as dump trucks or gondola dump truck) that connect material banks with consumption centers, such as infrastructure projects or production plants. Their performance depends on multiple factors: load capacity, routes used, operational efficiency, regulatory compliance, and quality of service. In regional contexts like Villahermosa, Tabasco, these lines play a strategic role in economic development due to their direct connection with the construction sector.

The competitiveness

This is understood as the ability of an organization, sector, or territory to offer products or services efficiently and sustainably, maintaining or increasing its market share in comparison to its competitors. The concept goes beyond mere cost control; it also encompasses elements such as innovation, productivity, operational flexibility, quality, environmental sustainability, and the capacity to adapt to changing environments (CEPAL, 2021).

In the case of aggregate transport lines, competitiveness involves the ability to make on-time deliveries, optimize resources such as fuel and labor, incorporate fleet monitoring and management technologies, and ensure safety and traceability in operations. Thus, a company becomes more competitive to the extent that it can meet these requirements efficiently and profitably (Benítez, 2012).

Measuring Competitiveness

Measuring competitiveness requires evaluating multiple dimensions, both internal and external. Internal factors include the level of operational organization, staff training, cost structure, technology adoption, and logistics processes. External factors involve the quality of road infrastructure, sector regulations, market conditions, and the institutional environment.

To capture this complexity, analytical models are used to diagnose strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in relation to the factors that influence competitiveness. Some models focus on the structural conditions of the market, such as Porter's Five Forces (Díaz, 2009); others emphasize systemic interactions, like Porter's Diamond Model; and some incorporate expert perception to prioritize critical factors, such as the Delphi method. The choice of an appropriate model depends on the analysis context, data availability, and the specific objectives of each study.

2. METHODOLOGY

The central objective of this research is to obtain a comprehensive result that allows for a structured and contextualized measurement of the competitiveness level of aggregate transport lines in Villahermosa, Tabasco. These lines represent a key component of the regional supply chain, and their competitive performance directly influences the efficiency of both public and private infrastructure projects in the region.

To achieve this objective, it is necessary to adopt a methodological approach that analyzes not only operational and economic conditions, but also the strategic, organizational, and technological factors that determine the sector’s competitiveness.

This approach must be capable of identifying and prioritizing the key factors influencing the performance of these lines, such as operating costs, logistical efficiency, level of digitalization, regulatory conditions, and the quality of human capital. However, the nature of the sector, characterized by high variability in management, limited access to systematized quantitative information, and the influence of contextual conditions, demands a methodology that goes beyond and integrates technical or statistical analyses. In this regard, it is essential to incorporate the expert opinion of those directly involved in the transport lines, whose accumulated practical experience constitutes valuable tacit knowledge for understanding the true determinants of competitiveness in the local context.

Thus, the present methodology seeks to select a solid analytical tool with participatory mechanisms, enabling a more realistic, prioritized, and useful diagnosis for the future formulation of effective improvement proposals, adapted to the actual conditions of the transport sector in Villahermosa.

Figure 1. Applied Methodology

3. RESULTS

This section presents the results obtained from the application of the methodology designed to select the most suitable tool for evaluating the competitiveness of aggregate transport lines in Villahermosa, Tabasco. Through a sequential and comparative approach, various theoretical models were analyzed in order to identify the one that best integrates both the sector’s operational conditions and the expert knowledge of its stakeholders. The findings reflect not only the methodological relevance of the adopted approach but also the richness of human capital present within the transport lines, whose contributions provided key insights into the real dynamics affecting competitiveness. This section offers a detailed overview of the analytical process followed, as well as the elements that supported the selection of the core method and/or tool for conducting the competitiveness diagnosis.

Definition of the Study Area

The study area focuses on the analysis of competitiveness within the transportation sector, specifically in the aggregate transport lines operating in the city of Villahermosa, Tabasco. These lines are part of the Federation of Trucks and Dump Trucks, a regional organization that brings together companies dedicated to the transportation of heavy materials for the construction industry. The strategic importance of this activity in local economic development, as well as its direct connection with road infrastructure and logistical costs, justifies its selection as the object of study.

Definition of the Study Universe

The study universe is composed of the 11 transport lines affiliated with the Federation, each with different operational capacities, types of fleets, years in the market, and levels of professionalization. It was identified that each line includes individuals with specialized knowledge, such as owners, logistics managers, and technical operators, who have more than 10 years of experience in the sector. This human capital is considered essential for understanding the critical factors of competitiveness from an empirical and contextualized perspective.

Identification of Analytical Tools

Once the study universe was defined and the specific characteristics of the transportation sector in Villahermosa were understood, the next step was to identify the most recognized models and methodological tools for analyzing competitiveness in organizations or productive sectors.

Based on a systematic review of academic literature, five analytical models were selected, each with a history of application in similar sectors, particularly transportation, logistics, manufacturing, and small enterprises across Latin America.

The selected models for analysis were as follows:

- **Porter's Five Forces Model:** This model, proposed by Michael Porter (1980), analyzes the competitive dynamics of a sector through five key elements: the bargaining power of customers, the bargaining power of suppliers, the threat of new entrants, the threat of substitute products, and the rivalry among existing competitors. Its application facilitates a structural understanding of the external pressures faced by companies within an industry.
- **Porter's Diamond Model:** Also known as the national or competitive diamond model, this framework developed by Michael Porter focuses on the factors that explain the competitive advantage of industries within a region or country. It considers four main determinants: factor conditions (infrastructure and resources), demand conditions, related and supporting industries, and firm strategy, structure, and rivalry. Additionally, it includes auxiliary variables such as government and chance.
- **Competitiveness Map of the Inter-American Development Bank (IDB):** This model aims to identify key capabilities and constraints that influence the competitiveness of strategic sectors in Latin America. The map considers aspects such as logistics infrastructure, the quality of the institutional framework, human capital, access to innovation, and financing. Its approach has been especially applied in studies on value chains and sectoral performance.
- **Organizational Competitiveness Diagnostic Model (DCO) by Martín Álvarez (1999):** This model proposes a comprehensive approach to evaluating an organization's competitiveness by assessing its

internal capabilities in relation to the external environment. It uses tools such as SWOT analysis, benchmarking, functional analysis, and internal process review. The model is oriented toward strategic decision-making within organizations.

- **Delphi Method:** The Delphi method is a structured expert consultation technique designed to generate consensus on complex topics through successive rounds of anonymous feedback. It relies on the participation of a panel of specialists who, through repeated evaluations, help identify, classify, and prioritize relevant factors in contexts where knowledge is dispersed or systematized statistical information is lacking.

Once the models were described, the next stage involved their methodological comparison, taking into account their applicability within the local context of the transport lines affiliated with the Federation of Trucks and Dump Trucks of Villahermosa.

Comparison of Analytical Tools

Based on the tools identified in the previous stage, a systematic comparison of the five candidate models was carried out, using their original purpose as a reference and assessing their level of applicability to the current study. For this comparison, three main dimensions were considered:

- Adaptability to the local context of the transport lines affiliated with the Federation of Trucks and Dump Trucks of Villahermosa
- Technical and informational requirements for implementation
- Methodological capacity to generate useful inputs for the formulation of improvement proposals

The following table summarizes the elements analyzed for each model:

Table 1. Comparison of Analytical Tools

CANDIDATE MODEL	ORIGINAL PURPOSE	STRENGTHS	LIMITATIONS FOR THE PRESENT STUDY
Porter’s Five Forces	Analyze the competitive structure of the sector	Simplicity; identifies external pressures (customers, suppliers, etc.)	Does not weigh the relative importance of each factor nor incorporate expert judgment
Porter’s Diamond	Explain national/sectoral competitive advantages	Systemic approach; integrates demand, factor conditions, and rivalry	Requires high availability of statistical data and does not prioritize variables
IDB Competitiveness Map	Measure regional performance in infrastructure, talent, and institutions	Latin American framework; comparable indicators	Requires public databases that are not available at the micro-enterprise level
DCO Model (Martín Álvarez)	Organizational Competitiveness Diagnosis	Combines benchmarking and SWOT; useful for intra-company analysis	Requires internal historical data, which the transport lines lack
Delphi Method	Build expert consensus on complex issues	Iterative, anonymous, weighs factors, adaptable to limited data	Requires organization of rounds and statistical analysis of responses

Based on this comparison, the following observations can be made:

- **Structural models** such as Porter's Diamond or the IDB Competitiveness Map offer solid macro or sector-level frameworks, but they require standardized and updated statistical data that is not available in most local transport lines, which often lack formal operational record-keeping processes.
- **Porter's Five Forces model**, while useful for describing the intensity of sectoral competition, does not allow for the prioritization of key factors nor the inclusion of expert judgment as a validated tool within the analytical process.
- **The DCO model by Martín Álvarez** has an internal and operational focus, but it is more suited to organizations with consolidated administrative structures and access to historical indicators—conditions that are not present in the companies under study, which mostly operate with flexible or semi-informal schemes.
- **Finally, the Delphi method** stands out as an adaptable tool that does not require large volumes of statistical data and draws upon the accumulated experience of sector stakeholders. Its ability to generate expert consensus through iterative rounds makes it an ideal instrument for identifying and prioritizing key competitiveness variables in an operational environment such as that of aggregate transport lines.

This comparison made it possible to advance to the next methodological stage: the final selection of the analytical tool, justified not only by its theoretical foundations but also by its practical relevance and adaptability to the real conditions of the study subject.

Selection of the Analytical Tool

After completing the identification and comparison of methodological models, the most suitable tool was selected to evaluate the competitiveness of aggregate transport lines. This decision was supported by a technical analysis based on five key criteria, defined according to the research objectives and the specific characteristics of the study universe.

Methodological Evaluation Criteria:

1. **Adaptability to the Local Context:** The degree to which the model can be applied to transport lines with informal or semi-formal organizational structures.
2. **Prioritization Capacity:** The model's ability to rank critical competitiveness factors based on their impact.
3. **Expert Participation:** The possibility of incorporating the judgment of actors with direct experience in the sector.
4. **Data Requirements:** The level of demand for statistical or historical data for its implementation.
5. **Applicability for Improvement:** The ability to generate practical and actionable results aimed at formulating improvement proposals.

Based on these criteria, a technical scoring matrix was developed, assigning values from 1 to 5, where 1 represents a low correspondence with the criterion and 5 represents a high correspondence.

Table 2. Technical Evaluation Matrix of Methodological Models

MODEL	LOCAL ADAPTABILITY	PRIORITIZATION OF FACTORS	EXPERT INTEGRATION	DATA REQUIREMENTS	PRACTICAL APPLICABILITY	TOTAL SCORE
Porter’s Five Forces	3	2	1	4	2	12
Porter’s Diamond	3	2	2	2	3	12
IDB Competitiveness Map	2	3	2	1	3	11
DCO Model (Martín Álvarez)	2	3	2	2	3	12
Delphi Method	5	5	5	4	5	24

As shown in the table above, the Delphi method obtained the highest score (24 points), clearly outperforming the other models across all key dimensions of this research. Its methodological structure, based on iterative rounds of expert consultation, allows for the following:

- Capture the tacit knowledge accumulated through years of field experience.
- Prioritize, in a participatory manner, the factors that affect local competitiveness.
- Adapt to an environment where the availability of quantitative data is limited or non-standardized.
- Generate a solid input for the formulation of improvement strategies based on reliable qualitative evidence.

Moreover, the Delphi tool not only meets the analytical criteria but also strengthens the legitimacy of the evaluation process by directly involving key stakeholders from the sector. This participatory approach increases the acceptance of results and their usefulness for future decision-making within the Federation. For these reasons, the Delphi method was selected as the central tool for developing the competitiveness diagnosis of the transport lines under study.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The selection of the Delphi method as the primary tool for evaluating the competitiveness of aggregate transport lines in Villahermosa, Tabasco, represents a methodological decision grounded in both analytical and contextual criteria. In other words, it was a decision based on an orderly methodological process that combined technical analysis with a deep understanding of the real-world context in which these lines operate.

From the outset, it was recognized that the sector has particular characteristics: loosely formalized administrative structures, limited availability of statistical data, highly diverse operations across transport lines, but also a wealth of practical knowledge accumulated over the years.

Based on this initial diagnosis, various widely recognized methodological tools were explored, such as Porter’s Five Forces, Porter’s Diamond, the IDB Competitiveness Map, and the DCO Model by Martín Álvarez, all of which have proven useful in more structured contexts. However, in the case of this study, their technical requirements and macroeconomic or institutional orientation made their direct application difficult in an environment where information is limited and expert judgment plays a key role.

In response to this, the Delphi method emerged as a more flexible, participatory, and suitable alternative for the type of analysis required. Its main advantage lies in its ability to build a collective diagnosis based on the knowledge of those directly involved in the daily operations of transport. The anonymous rounds of expert consultation help generate consensus on the most important factors affecting competitiveness and allow for refining responses based on shared experience.

This approach not only offers a technical solution but also represents a different way of valuing knowledge in research. It is not merely about seeking hard data, but about recognizing that experience is also a valid and necessary source for understanding and improving organizational processes.

This perspective aligns with current participatory evaluation approaches, which emphasize the importance of building solutions from within, incorporating the voices of those who live and understand the realities of the sector.

In conclusion, the applied methodology and the selection of the Delphi method lay the foundation for a more comprehensive, realistic, and useful analysis of the sector's competitiveness. This approach not only helps identify weaknesses but also prioritizes key factors and proposes improvement actions that align with the actual capabilities and opportunities of the transport lines in Villahermosa. Beyond diagnosis, the Delphi method becomes a tool for collectively building solutions, with the potential to be replicated in other sectors with similar dynamics.

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